

19. Hotel Managers Perceptions of Sustainable Tourism Certification Systems: Insights from Turkish and Irish Professionals

Dr. Conor McTiernan, Assoc. Prof. Dr. Mehlika Saraç,
Prof. Dr. Aylin POROY ARSOY, Dr. Pádraig Gallaghe

ABSTRACT:

Sustainable tourism certification systems, such as GSTC and the supporting criteria, are gaining increasing traction in hospitality scholarship. Such research focuses on three distinct yet interrelated themes. Firstly, their impacts on hospitality operations, particularly their contribution to the 'measure and manage' approach to waste and water usage, carbon emission reduction, financial implications and hospitality's contribution to the circular economy. Secondly, sustainable certification systems' cumulative impacts on the development of sustainable destinations. Finally, the literature examines the role of top-down initiatives to support hospitality organisations adaptation of credible sustainability certification programmes to ensure the sector complies with regional, national and international agendas such as Net-Zero. Yet there remains a dearth of research in the perceptions and motivations of the key gatekeepers to successful adoption of certification programmes; the hotel managers. Using the value-norm-belief model, this research captures perceptions of hotel managers' insights on the challenges, benefits and credibility of implementing GSTC certification from three perspectives. Firstly, their self-efficacy that they have an ethical duty to adopt such criteria to effect positive change. Secondly, the data explores the impact of social norms on their engagement with certification programmes and finally, the impact of legislative calls to employ such systems on their operations, employees and customer satisfaction.

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Conor McTiernan (PhD) is a lecturer in the Department of Tourism and Sport in Atlantic Technological University. He completed his PhD in Leeds Beckett University exploring the role of trust in inter-organisational knowledge transfer in Irish festival and event tourism networks. Conor's teaching and research primarily focuses on sustainable tourism policy development, tourism networks, innovation, knowledge management and trust in tourism SMTE's. Conor is also knowledgeable on tourism network formation and operation, especially facilitating knowledge transfer within network structures. Conor is a member the Irish Hospitality Institute, the First International Network of Trust and serves as the co-chair on the tourism committee for the Laurentic Forum, a network of Irish, Icelandic, Norwegian and Canadian tourism policy makers and practitioners dedicated to the development of a sustainable tourism sector that supports coastal communities.

Mehlika Saraç is Associate Professor of Bursa Uludag University Faculty of Economics and Administrative Sciences, Business Administration Department. Her research interests are in cross-cultural studies,

sustainability, and social entrepreneurship. She has been teaching in bachelor, master and PhD degrees on management, social entrepreneurship and organizational behaviour.

Aylin POROY ARSOY is Professor of Bursa Uludag University Faculty of Economics and Administrative Sciences. She has conducted cross-cultural studies with different parties and has several academic studies, mainly on financial reporting, transparency, corporate governance. She has been teaching in bachelor, master and PhD degrees on financial accounting, international accounting, integrated reporting, corporate governance since 2008.

Dr Pádraig Gallagher has over 20 years' experience in the higher education sector and is currently the Head of Research & Innovation at the Atlantic Technological University Donegal, Ireland. He has a strong track record of European & industry/academia collaborative projects, sources of funding for research, innovation and the commercialisation process, knowledge transfer and enterprise development. Research interests include, employability, SME competitiveness, entrepreneurship, higher education, and industry interaction.